

Article

Running toward Sustainability: Exploring Off-Peak Destination Resilience through a Mixed-Methods Approach—The Case of Sporting Events

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Abstract: The sustainability of tourism activities faces many challenges. Furthermore, in the context of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their overall slow progress, tourism-related goals and targets are underachieved. To address these challenges, this study has recognized sporting events as an opportunity to enhance the socio-economic activities in tourism destinations during off-season periods. More specifically, the aim of this study is to explore the dynamics of off-season destination resilience through small-scale running events, focusing on three key aspects: the strategies employed by organizers, the synergy created within the community, and the sustainable outcomes. Drawing on insights from qualitative interviews with twenty-five running event organizers across Greece, supported by the Delphi method to confirm and validate the results, their perceptions of the economic and socio-cultural dimensions are explored. This study identifies a number of strategies that enrich running events and can contribute to the sustainability of off-peak destinations. Additionally, the concept of synergy is identified and explored, emphasizing the importance of local engagement, participant encouragement, and community collaborations. These findings provide a comprehensive understanding of how these factors can influence the sustainability of off-peak destinations. To further validate and extend these findings, the second part of this study performs a quantitative analysis using PLS-SEM, involving eighty local authorities in Greece. The results highlight the mediating role of small-scale event enrichment strategies on the relationship between synergy and destination sustainability. This multifaceted approach indicates the dynamics of sustainable tourism, by examining the case of small-scale running events in the off-peak season. The impact of this balanced approach on the broader achievement of relevant SDGs is also supported. The implications of this research, in terms of its strategic and stakeholder orientation for tourism professionals and government agencies, are also discussed.

Keywords: sustainability; organizers; seasonality; PLS-SEM; destination resilience; local authorities; running; SDGs

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1. Introduction

Tourism is the third largest economic activity in the world, accounting for 10% of global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and providing one in ten jobs worldwide [1]. It can undoubtedly contribute, directly or indirectly, to all the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Scholars have long advocated that small-scale sports events can play a crucial role in fostering sustainable tourism development within communities [2], particularly in addressing the challenge of seasonality in the tourism sector [3]. This study focuses on the running movement in Greece, which has grown significantly over the last 30 years, promoting physical activity and the sustainability of the country's sports tourism economy; Greece now hosts a variety of running events, from international marathons to smaller local races, reflecting the vitality of the country's running community [4].

Against this background, there have been attempts to navigate the dynamics of running events within the sphere of sustainable tourism, with a particular focus on off-peak periods. A mixed-method approach is used, covering multiple stakeholders. To develop and validate the constructs of the structural model, qualitative data was collected through semi-structured interviews with running event organizers. The interviews with these experts revealed certain strategies and their impact on the sustainable development of localities.

After this phase, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) tested and validated the qualitative data. The sample consisted of local authorities (municipalities), with the view to assess the resonance of organizers' perspectives within the broader community that is these key destination management stakeholders. The research framework is centered on four hypotheses, which all contribute to the understanding of the relationship between sport event enrichment strategies, synergy, and sustainability within the off-season period. Through this mixed-methods design, this study not only uncovers unique insights but also validates and extends these perspectives, providing an evidence-based exploration of the sustainable development in the context of small-scale running events within the off-season period.

To the best of our knowledge, this study represents one of the first efforts to explore the direct and mediating relationships within the context of running events and synergy, with a primary focus on assessing their impact on sustainability during the low season, using PLS-SEM as the main data analysis methodology.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1. Background of the Study

Tourism-related targets are included in Goals 8, 12 and 14 on inclusive and sustainable economic growth, sustainable consumption and production, and sustainable use of oceans and marine resources [5]. Promoting responsible and sustainable tourism management can lead to job creation, foster economic diversification, and contribute to the preservation of marine ecosystems, thus aligning with the SDG goals 8, 12, and 14 [5]. Travelling during off-peak periods is deemed a sustainable practice because it contributes to the utilization of transport and accommodation which would otherwise be idle during particular times of the year when common tourist attractions are absent [6]. Strategizing and advertising activities promoting off-peak tourism enhance the worth of existing sites and amenities relying on infrastructure and other resources that would otherwise be underutilized and increasing employability [6].

The World Tourism Organization considers tourism seasonality as a fundamental concern in relation to the sustainability of tourism [7]. Seasonality exerts environmental impacts by straining natural resources, increasing pollution, interfering with ecosystems, and generating noise pollution, while also causing adverse economic effects such as inefficient facility utilization, diminished company profits in low seasons, and restricted investment in the tourism sector [8]. Thus, tourism seasonality appears as a major challenge for the sustainable development in tourism destinations, as it leads to uneven distribution of tourist arrivals throughout the year, causing a variety of negative economic, ecological and community impacts [9]. Off-peak tourism's reliance on peak seasons poses sustainability challenges, causing environmental issues, conflicts, and over-tourism concerns; economic determinants, especially income and costs, influence seasonality, requiring strategic measures for sustainable tourism [10].

Academics have consistently recognized the potential of small-scale sporting events to contribute significantly to the sustainable development of tourism within local communities; small-scale sport events are minor annual events where competitors may outnumber spectators, attracting limited national media interest and economic activity compared to large-scale events [2]. Among them, running events are shown to have a clear role in sustainable tourism by engaging tourists in a more localized and recurring manner, in contrast to large-scale sporting events that change locations frequently [11]. Lower-ranked running events seem to be particularly effective in driving additional tourism activities in

the host city and positively impacting its image, while they have a clear role in sustainable tourism because of their localized and recurring nature [11]. Regularly organizing small-scale running events can act as a catalyst for local sustainable development by efficiently utilizing existing resources, fostering community involvement, and ensuring a consistent influx of visitors [12]. However, it is important to organize running events not only in urban centers, but also in rural areas, to cater to the diverse needs of participants and promote physical activity, health, and enjoyment in different regions [13].

Previous studies in the field of sports tourism and sustainable tourism have focused on different aspects. For example, a study on Mallorca focuses on the development of a wealth-generating business model that promotes sustainable, environmentally friendly and deseasonalized tourism in overcrowded destinations, and also aims to create synergies between sport, sustainability, and gender equality, while addressing the need for innovative tourism models to reduce seasonality [14]. Another sustainability study examines the multiple impacts of sports events, focusing on social and environmental aspects in addition to the traditional economic impacts [15]. Other researchers developed a sustainability-focused business model for sport tourism destinations, integrating supply chain management principles and a sustainability-balanced scorecard to assess five key perspectives in order to guide destination managers seeking to promote sustainable sport tourism practices [16]. Also, research in sport related areas found that environmental campaigns can effectively promote sustainable transport choices, and organizers should focus on fostering community connections and providing transportation information [17]. Recent research proposes a theoretical framework for sustainable communication in sport tourism, emphasizing the efficacy of communication in fostering sustainable behaviors and promoting sustainable development [18].

2.2. Exploring Organizers' Perceptions

In the current study, a research gap within sport event organizers, particularly in the sustainability of the running events, has been identified. For example, scholarly works have produced instruments for assessing event organizers' perceptions of the socio-economic impacts on local communities [19], delved into organizers' perspectives on attendee motivations [20], and explored challenges related to ambush marketing for organizers of major global sporting events [21]. More recent studies, such as the one presented in [22], have focused on validating a mobile application water planning tool for road race event organizers.

However, agreement among stakeholders, encompassing municipal authorities, local communities, and organizers is imperative to setting destination development goals, ensuring not only the success of the race but, more importantly, the sustained and sustainable development of the destination [23]. Acknowledging the importance of engaging multiple stakeholders in the planning process, event tourism researchers have called for more investigation from the perspective of event organizers and investors [24]. Given the influential role of relationships between organizers and stakeholders on event quality [25], and recognizing the significance of organizers focusing on controllable factors [26], this study addresses the gap in the context of running events. Thus, it contributes to discussions on organizers' perceptions, specifically addressing the strategies employed for the sustainability for running event destinations during off-season period. Throughout this article, the term 'small-scale running events' is used to refer to various running competitions, including 5 km races, half marathons, marathons, fun races, road races, and mountain races. The intention is to encompass the diverse spectrum of running events within the study, all of which fall under the umbrella of running sports.

2.3. Running-Event Organizers' Interviews

This study firstly employs an exploratory research method, aiming to delve into the dynamics of small-scale running events in the context of destination sustainability during off-peak seasons. As a first step, interviews with running event organizers all around

Greece were conducted, covering a variety of running events ranging from 5 km races to marathons, including fun races, road races, and mountain races. The interview questions focused on exploring running events' local impact, community engagement for off-season sustainability, and strategies to enrich low-season running events, as follows:

- How does the off-season running event enhance local destination sustainability, encompassing both economic and socio-cultural aspects?
- In what ways do you involve the local community in the organization of the event to enhance destination sustainability during the off-season?
- What strategies do you find most effective in enriching a running event to thrive during the low-season while promoting sustainability?

These semi-structured questions allowed for in-depth responses, offering valuable qualitative data on the organizers' perspectives and practices related to destination sustainability during off-peak periods. The study was implemented in the early phases of the post-pandemic recovery process, when capturing fresh perspectives was important. The research sample comprised twenty-five passionate small-scale running-event organizers actively engaged in the planning and execution of sports events. These Greek organizers, united by their love for sports, are dedicated to providing optimal sporting experiences for athletes. A central objective for them is to showcase the natural beauty of their hometowns, establishing running events that will serve as catalysts for both sports and entertainment within their local communities.

The selected destinations for these events are marked by pronounced tourism seasonality, with the organizers strategically planning events during the middle or low seasons. This deliberate choice allows them to contribute to the sustainability of their communities and promote sports engagement beyond peak tourist periods. Notably, the majority of the interviewed organizers are permanent residents of the areas under investigation, underscoring their deep connection and active involvement in the community. The study involved both online and onsite interviews with the purposive sample in order to reach a diverse range of urban, seaside, mountain, and rural Greek regions and ensure that organizers in remote areas are not overlooked and geographical constraints are overcome.

The qualitative findings from the interviews were subjected to validation through the Delphi method, which is a crucial research tool in sustainable tourism development. Utilizing a panel of industry experts, the Delphi method serves as an effective forecasting tool, widely accepted and precise, and addresses the challenge of ensuring sustainability [27]. In the Delphi method employed for this study, two rounds were conducted to gather insights from a panel of seven running event experts. The primary aim of these rounds was to explore how the panel interpreted the feedback received after the initial interviews and to assess the content validity of the conceptual entities related to the sustainability of running events.

The subsequent phase involved the confirmation of these insights through the perspectives of local authorities in Greece. This multifaceted approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the sustainable implications of running events during off-peak periods. Finally, it is essential to note that this study is a segment of a more extensive and long-term research initiative exploring sustainable approaches to mitigate seasonality in the context of small-scale running events.

2.4. Conceptual Framework: Running Event Organizers' Perspectives

In the qualitative exploration of the perspectives of running event organizers, distinct themes emerged, capturing their perceptions and practices in three overarching categories: Sustainability, Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES), and Synergy (Figure 1), as follows:

Figure 1. The proposed model and hypothesized paths.

2.4.1. Sustainability

The focal point of this investigation is sustainability, a construct encompassing four key elements: Income Increase (SUST1), Employment Opportunities Increase (SUST2), Investment in new facilities (SUST3), and Leisure Opportunities (SUST4). This variable serves as a lens through which the impact of running events on local communities, particularly during low-season periods in the destination, is examined. The four key elements are analyzed below:

- Income Increase (SUST1) is a pivotal dimension that organizers and existing literature affirm as a significant outcome of running events. Foundational studies, such as the seminal work of Walo et al. [28], highlighted that the economic influx generated during an athletic event extends far and beyond mere participation fees. Expenditure on food services, accommodations, and shopping activities by athletes and visitors significantly contributes to the financial well-being of the local community. This economic stimulation is particularly pronounced during off-season weekends, providing an extra and crucial income boost for local businesses.
- Employment Opportunities Increase (SUST2) emerges as another vital component of sustainability. The organization of running events generates a rise in demand for services, prompting the hiring of additional staff by professionals during event days. The race becomes a catalyst for job creation and the extension of existing employment contracts, aligning with the objective of providing enhanced services to the influx of visitors. This economic activity during low-season periods contributes substantially to the financial stability of locals.
- Investment in new facilities (SUST3) marks a tangible outcome of the economic impact of running events. Local professionals and the community, recognizing the heightened demand during event days, invest in new facilities. The financial footprint of the event, as emphasized by organizers, plays a crucial role in inspiring these investments, leading to sustained development beyond the event period.
- Leisure Opportunities (SUST4) extend beyond the sporting activities and enhance community well-being. The positive social value generated by running events is evidenced by the increased collaboration and voluntary efforts of the local society. From the creation of a festive atmosphere to the initiation of running consciousness among individuals, the race becomes a basis for fostering social cohesion, cooperation, and communication among locals.

2.4.2. Sport Event Enrichment Strategies

Event organizers recognized the following five key elements, which constitute the variable Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) and which are implemented to broaden the impact and appeal of the running event, encouraging participant engagement and contributing to the overall sustainability of the destination:

- Tour Activities (Tours in the Area, Natural and Historical Sights, etc.) (SEES1) variable involves the strategic integration of guided tours and walks to showcase the region's cultural and natural treasures. Organizers aim to provide a unique experience for participants while promoting the local culture and heritage through exploring natural trails and cultural routes, enhancing the overall race extension strategy.
- Exhibitions with Local Products of the Region (SEES2) variable indicates that organizers plan events and fairs to complement the race, showcasing the region's local products, cuisine, and cultural elements. These exhibitions entertain participants and visitors, contributing to the promotion of local traditions and fostering a deeper connection between the event and the community.
- Regarding Fun and Actions for All Visitors (Athletes, Escorts, Family) (SEES3) variable, organizers recognize the diverse needs of participants and their families; thus, they introduce additional activities for non-participants, including options like yoga, swimming, music bands, children's playgrounds, and traditional dance clubs. The goal is to create a holistic experience that caters to a wide audience, making the event enjoyable for everyone involved.
- The variable Social Media Marketing (SEES4) emphasizes the important role of social media in event promotion. Organizers acknowledge the importance of platforms like Instagram and Facebook for publicity and reputation building. Despite variations in social media proficiency, the consensus is that an effective online presence significantly contributes to event success and visibility, underlining the dynamic nature of digital marketing.
- In the context of Sport Websites Administration/Use (SEE5), organizers leverage websites to promote races, aiming to enhance participant experience and streamline registration processes. Engaging with well-known running websites amplifies the visibility of their events within the broader running community. While some focus on the continuous improvement of their websites, others prioritize official platforms to reach a wider audience, showcasing the interconnectedness of technology and race promotion.
- The variable Love for the Birthplace (SEE6) underscores organizers' shared passion and pride for their race locations. Their love for the region serves as a driving force behind their commitment to contribute to local tourism development. This emotional connection motivates efforts to showcase the unique features of their birthplaces, fostering a sense of responsibility for environmental protection and community engagement.

In summary, Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (RES) encompass a multifaceted approach to enhance the running event's sustainable impact, emphasizing diverse initiatives such as guided tours, exhibitions, and engaging activities. These strategies aim to create a unique and inclusive experience for participants, foster community connections, and promote the destination's cultural and natural assets. The diverse range of strategies employed by organizers demonstrates their commitment to enhancing the overall race experience, promoting local culture, and contributing to the sustainable development of off-peak destinations.

2.4.3. Synergy

The construct "Synergy" integrates four key elements that contribute to the holistic event experience. This synergy is built upon crucial aspects, such as the guidance from local authorities, embedding running culture, providing motives, and establishing special agreements to enrich the event and its local impact, and is analyzed as follows:

- The directions from authorities (SYN1) variable reflects the organizers' desire for local authorities' guidance in developing sustainable initiatives within the community. They seek transparency, long-term planning, and cooperation from authorities to enhance the event's quality and expand activities, yet express frustration due to limited support and resources, hindering their ability to enrich the event experience.
- The variable Running Culture (SYN2) elucidates the local engagement, perception, and the community's attitude toward running. The comments emphasized the necessity

for a vibrant local running culture. The organizers underscored that lack of local enthusiasm for running presented a challenge for the event and the community, inhibiting local engagement and support.

- The variable Participant Encouragement (SYN3) within the construct of Synergy is centered on the strategies employed to motivate participants, encouraging their return to the event and the region. Collaboration among multiple stakeholders aims to create attractive incentives for the athletes and visitors, offering special gifts, medals, discounts, and additional benefits.
- The variable Community Collaborations (SYN4) epitomizes the strategic partnerships established by event organizers with local stakeholders. These alliances involve negotiated arrangements such as discounted services, unique offers, and cooperative ventures.

The Synergy elements demonstrate a commitment to sustainability, as reflected in the organizers' perceptions.

In conclusion, the qualitative exploration of running event organizers' perspectives reveals a variety of practices and perceptions that shape the sustainability, enrichment strategies, and synergy of small-scale running events. Sustainability emerges as a multifaceted construct, encompassing economic, employment, investment, and leisure dimensions, highlighting the profound impact of running events on local communities, particularly during off-peak periods. Sport Event Enrichment Strategies showcase diverse initiatives, from guided tours to social media marketing, underscoring organizers' commitment to creating unique and inclusive experiences and contributing to the overall sustainability of destinations. The category of Synergy unveils crucial elements, which collectively contribute to a symbiotic event experience during low-season period. These findings serve as a robust foundation for constructing the main hypotheses that will examine the direct and mediating relationships between Sport Event Enrichment Strategies, Synergy, and Off-Peak Destination Sustainability.

2.5. Hypotheses Evolution

Continuing with the formulation of hypotheses, the aim is to articulate and test key propositions that elucidate the intricate connections between the constructs. The current investigation revolves around the Sustainability (SUS) construct, consisting of four key elements:

- Income Increase (SUST1): Running events significantly boost local income, especially off-season.
- Employment Opportunities Increase (SUST2): Organizing events creates jobs, enhancing local financial stability, especially in the low-season.
- Investment in New Facilities (SUST3): Event demand leads to community investment, sustaining economic development.
- Leisure Opportunities (SUST4): Running events foster social ties, providing leisure opportunities beyond sports.

Organizers implement Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) to broaden the impact and appeal of running events. Key initiatives include:

- Tour Activities (SEES1): Strategic integration of guided tours and walks showcasing the region's cultural and natural treasures, enhancing the overall race extension strategy.
- Exhibitions with Local Products (SEES2): Planning events and fairs to complement the race, showcasing local products, cuisine, and cultural elements, contributing to the promotion of local traditions.
- Fun and Activities for All Visitors (SEES3): Recognizing diverse needs, organizers introduce additional activities for non-participants, creating a holistic experience for everyone involved.
- Social Media Marketing Skills (SEES4): Acknowledging the pivotal role of social media in event promotion, organizers leverage platforms like Instagram and Facebook for publicity, emphasizing the dynamic nature of digital marketing.

- Sport Websites Administration/Use (RES5): Utilizing websites to enhance participant experience, streamline registration processes, and amplify event visibility within the broader running community.

Building on the aforementioned insights, the following hypothesis is generated:

Hypothesis 1 (H1). *Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) have a positive direct effect on Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST).*

Synergy represents a holistic event experience built upon crucial elements, including sustainability-oriented strategies, as below:

- Guidance from Local Authorities (SYN1): Organizers seek clearer guidance, transparency, and cooperation from local authorities for sustainable event development.
- Building Running Culture (SYN2): Emphasis on cultivating a vibrant local running culture and addressing challenges related to the lack of local enthusiasm for running.
- Participant Encouragement (SYN3): Strategies employed to motivate participants, fostering collaboration among stakeholders to create compelling incentives for athletes and visitors.
- Community Collaborations (SYN4): Strategic partnerships established by organizers with local stakeholders, involving negotiated arrangements and cooperative ventures.

Therefore, the following hypotheses are generated:

Hypothesis 2 (H2). *Synergy (SYN) has a positive direct effect on Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST).*

Hypothesis 3 (H3). *Synergy (SYN) has a positive direct effect on Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES).*

Building upon the foundational underpinnings of this study exploring the interplay between Synergy and Sport Event Enrichment Strategies, the following hypothesis for mediation relationships is generated:

Hypothesis 4 (H4). *Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) mediate the relationship between Synergy (SYN) and Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST).*

3. Quantitative Methodology

The preliminary findings of this study underscored the importance of synergy and sport event enrichment strategies in achieving sustainability in tourism. To confirm the validity of the qualitative findings, a quantitative phase was then conducted. This subsequent phase involved engaging local authorities (Greek municipalities), specifically deputy mayors of tourism, who often serve as intermediaries between event organizers and the local community, with the aim of providing a robust foundation for our research outcomes. For this purpose, a survey questionnaire was used to gather the necessary data from the local authorities. A five-point Likert scale was employed with 'strongly disagree' corresponding to one and 'strongly agree' to five. The survey instrument was initially tested by four academics and four professionals from within the population (municipalities).

PLS-SEM served as the main data analysis procedure. This approach is suitable for investigating and validating the initial stages of theory development [29]. PLS-SEM allowed the assessment of validity in both measurement and structural models, given its suitability for multivariate analysis and its predictive capabilities even with a small sample size.

3.1. Scale and Measure Development

In this study, the scales employed were derived from the extensive examination of the perspectives of small-scale running event organizers, ensuring relevance and alignment with the context of this research. Drawing on the insights gathered from interviews with organizers, the development of scale items was undertaken to measure the key dimensions related to the event's impact on local sustainability during the low-season period. The variables assessed included Sport Event Enrichment Strategies, Synergy, and Sustainability elements.

The scale was validated by certain academics and professionals from within the population (municipalities) in order to ensure its appropriateness for capturing the organizers' views.

3.2. Participants and Collection of the Study Data

The sampling unit for this study comprised vice mayors overseeing tourist sports activities in their respective regions within Greece. The sample frame was determined using the official database of the Central Union of Municipalities of Greece, where a total of 332 municipalities was identified. The email addresses collected from this database facilitated the electronic invitations for participation in our survey questionnaire. The data was collected after COVID-19 pandemic, and 80 completed questionnaires out of the initial pool of 332 were received.

3.3. Data Analysis Techniques

Leguina's [30] two-step approach was followed to evaluate the collected data. First, the measurement model (referred to as the 'outer model') was tested for validity and reliability. Secondly, the structural model (referred to as the 'inner model') was evaluated to test the research hypotheses. The PLS-SEM method was chosen to test the research hypotheses, including the mediating effect of Sport Event Enrichment Strategies, due to its ability to handle multiple reflective items per construct without making assumptions about data distributions, outperforming other statistical methods such as CB-SEM in this regard [29].

3.3.1. Evaluation of the Measurement Model

To assess the outer model in PLS-SEM, the recommended threshold values proposed by Hair et al. [29,31] were applied for the standardized factor loadings (Loadings), the inner variance inflation factor (Inner VIF) the composite reliability (CR), and the average variance extracted (AVE). The measured and the corresponding threshold values for each parameter are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Assessment of the outer model's validity.

Items	Abbrev.	Loading	Inner VIF	a	CR	AVE
Suggested Cut-Off Level		at least 0.5 and ideally >0.7	>0.5	>0.7	>0.7	>0.5
Off-Peak Season Sustainability	SUST			0.812	0.877	0.641
Income Increase	SUST1	0.841				
Employment Opportunities Increase	SUST2	0.849				
New facilities Investment	SUST3	0.793				
Leisure Opportunities	SUST4	0.711				
Sport Event Enrichment Strategies	SSES		1.748	0.812	0.865	0.517
Tour Activities (Tours in the Area, Natural and Historical Sights, etc.)	SEES1	0.726				
Exhibitions with Local Products of the Region	SEES2	0.703				
Fun and Actions for All Visitors (Athletes, Escorts, Family)	SEES3	0.700				
Social Media Marketing Skills	SEES4	0.691				
Sport Websites Administration/Use	SEES5	0.815				
Love for the Birthplace	SEES6	0.670				
Synergy	SYN		1.000	0.732	0.831	0.553
Directions from authorities	SYN1	0.796				
Running Culture	SYN2	0.671				
Participant Encouragement	SYN3	0.719				
Community Collaborations	SYN4	0.783				

In this study, discriminant validity was assessed by three metrics as proposed by Leguina [18], i.e., (1) the cross-loadings, (2) the Fornell–Larcker criterion, and (3) the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) criterion (see Tables 2–4).

Table 2. Cross-loadings.

	SEES	SUST	SYN
SEES1	0.726	0.374	0.430
SEES2	0.703	0.472	0.420
SEES3	0.700	0.385	0.424
SEES4	0.691	0.451	0.493
SEES5	0.815	0.535	0.558
SEES6	0.670	0.372	0.477
SUST1	0.562	0.841	0.492
SUST2	0.474	0.849	0.553
SUST3	0.355	0.793	0.455
SUST4	0.527	0.711	0.418
SYN1	0.607	0.504	0.796
SYN2	0.373	0.474	0.671
SYN3	0.402	0.419	0.719
SYN4	0.528	0.389	0.783

Table 3. Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

	SEES	SUST	SYN
SEES	0.719		
SUST	0.607	0.801	
SYN	0.654	0.602	0.744

Table 4. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT).

	SEES	SUST	SYN
SEES	0.719		
SUST	0.607	0.801	
SYN	0.654	0.602	0.744

As presented in Table 2, each latent variable’s items loading (bolded) surpassed the respective cross-loadings (with other scale items).

The results support discriminant validity according to the Fornell-Larcker Criterion (Table 3).

According to Leguina’s guidelines [30], the HTMT value is expected to be below 0.90. The calculated HTMT values (as shown in Table 4) were indeed found to be below 0.90. These results indicate that the measures have sufficient reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity, so that the inner model can be evaluated next to test the research hypotheses.

3.3.2. Evaluation of the Structural Model (Hypotheses Testing)

Following the demonstration of convergent and discriminant validity of the measurement model, the structural model was evaluated (Figure 2). The focus was on explaining and predicting the effect of exogenous latent variables on the endogenous dependent latent

variables [32]. Several metrics were used to test the model's goodness of fit (GoF). To ensure a good model fit, the minimum acceptable R-squared value was 0.10 [29]. Accordingly, the endogenous latent variables, SEES and SYN had R-squared values of 0.428, and 0.442, respectively, supporting that the study model has adequate predictive power. Furthermore, the respective Stone-Geisser Q2 criteria scores were greater than zero (SEES, 0.121; SUST, 0.269), further supporting the predictive ability of the proposed model [33].

Figure 2. The structural model—SmartPLS output.

In the final stage of the PLS calculations, a bootstrapping analysis with 5000 iterations was performed to evaluate the path coefficient effects and the significance of t-values for both direct and mediating relationships (Table 5). This study proposed and examined three direct and one mediating hypotheses. The PLS-SEM findings revealed that Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) positively and significantly impact Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST) ($\beta = 0,373$, $t = 3.449$, $p > 0.001$); therefore, we can accept Hypothesis 1. Also, the findings revealed that Synergy (SYN) has a significant positive impact on Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST) ($\beta = 0,358$, $t = 3.074$, $p = 0.000$); so, we can accept Hypothesis 2. Additionally, Synergy (SYN) has a significant positive impact on Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) ($\beta = 0,654$, $t = 3.522$, $p > 0.001$) and H3 is therefore supported. For the mediating effects, the specific indirect effects in PLS-SEM revealed that Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) positively mediate the relationship between Synergy (SYN) and Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST) ($\beta = 0.244$, $t = 2.268$, $p = 0.024$).

Table 5. Hypotheses Assessment.

	β	t-Value	p-Value
Direct Path Coefficients			
H1: Sport Event Enrichment Strategies \rightarrow Off-Peak Destination Sustainability	0.373	3.449	0.001
H2: Synergy \rightarrow Off-Peak Destination Sustainability	0.358	3.074	0.002
H3: Synergy \rightarrow Sport Event Enrichment Strategies	0.654	3.522	0.000
Specific Indirect Effects			
H4: Synergy \rightarrow Sport Event Enrichment Strategies \rightarrow Off-Peak Destination Sustainability	0.244	2.268	0.024

4. Discussion and Implications

The empirical findings of this study demonstrate that this research successfully achieves its stated goals and objectives, making a significant contribution to the existing literature on sustainable development of off-peak destinations. Specifically, the findings

support the proposed hypotheses and also highlight the important role and the interconnectedness of Sport Event Enrichment Strategies and Synergy in fostering sustainable development during low-season periods.

The positive impact of Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) on Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST) emphasizes the centric role of event organizers in shaping sustainable outcomes. The findings suggest that strategic planning, diverse initiatives, and engagement activities employed by organizers not only enhance the overall event experience but also play a significant role in fostering sustainability within the destination during off-peak periods. This aligns with the growing recognition of the tourism industry's potential to drive sustainable development [34,35].

Also, the positive influence of Synergy (SYN) on Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST) underscores the importance of collaboration, community engagement, and strategic partnerships in achieving sustainable outcomes. The holistic event experience created through synergy, marked by transparent cooperation, local participation, and strategic collaborations, emerges as a driving force in sustaining destinations during off-peak seasons.

Moreover, the reciprocal relationship between Synergy (SYN) and Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) accentuates the interdependence of these elements. Organizers, by fostering synergy, can enhance their capacity to implement effective event enrichment strategies. This symbiotic relationship emphasizes the need for a holistic approach that combines community engagement, collaboration, and strategic planning to optimize the impact of event strategies on destination sustainability.

The mediating role of Sport Event Enrichment Strategies (SEES) in the relationship between Synergy (SYN) and Off-Peak Destination Sustainability (SUST) adds another layer to the discussion. It suggests that the positive impact of synergy on sustainability is, in part, realized through the implementation of event enrichment strategies. This underscores the instrumental role of these strategies in translating collaborative efforts and community engagement into tangible sustainable outcomes.

For event organizers, these insights offer actionable strategies to enhance the sustainability of small-scale running events during off-peak seasons. Local authorities can benefit from understanding their crucial role in providing guidance and support to organizers, fostering a vibrant running culture, and facilitating community collaborations. Communities stand to gain by actively participating in and supporting running events, contributing to the enrichment of local culture and economic vitality.

This study contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of event enrichment strategies and the significance of synergy in achieving sustainable outcomes. This enriches the discussion on sustainable tourism, particularly in the context of off-peak periods, and highlights the importance of integrating local perspectives into event planning and destination management. Local communities can take advantage of such initiatives to attract visitors, particularly in times when regular tourism activities slow down.

5. Conclusions and Future Research Directions

Overall, this research not only offers empirical evidence for the proposed hypotheses but also explores the complex dynamics of sustainable tourism within local communities, drawing on the illustration of small-scale running events. The findings of this study shed light on the multifaceted nature of sustainability in tourism and emphasize the interconnection between event strategies, synergy, and destination sustainability. The validated model underlines the importance of coordination and collaboration among various stakeholders in serving the strategic orientation of sustainability initiatives.

With regard to the SDGs, the model offers specific indicators that may help organizations to mature in terms of SDG materialization and add to their advancement. The slow progress or even decline in achieving the SDGs has raised concerns among strategists, governments and other stakeholders [36,37]. The need for measures toward improving SDG awareness and achievement is prevalent. This study's indicators align directly with

SDG target 8.9, which aims to create policies that foster sustainable tourism and support job creation while promoting local culture and products. In addition, the study has an indirect but important connection to SDG 4. By providing year-round employment opportunities for tourism-dependent businesses and places, it can help increase income and improve the security of vulnerable populations. From a technical perspective, the cost of maintaining infrastructure is spread over more months of operation, resulting in lower unit/month costs. This approach aims to address the socio-economic consequences of seasonal imbalances.

While this study adds value to the extant body of knowledge, it is not without limitations. The sample, although it represents the population, is specific to the Greek context. However, the study's cross-sectional design limits our ability to capture dynamic changes over time. Nevertheless, the results of this study can be generalized to destinations with comparable levels of seasonality in terms of tourism, particularly those where tourism is the primary or sole economic driver. It is also important to consider the multiplier effect on employment rates. Future research could investigate the transferability of these results to varying cultural and geographical contexts. Further research into off-peak tourism activities and their effects on sustainability would offer useful insights for hospitality and tourism professionals and other relevant stakeholders.

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References

1. WTTC—World Travel & Tourism Council. Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2022, Global Trends. 2022. Available online: <https://wtcc.org/Portals/0/Documents/Reports/2022/EIR2022-Global%20Trends.pdf> (accessed on 7 December 2023).
2. Gibson, H.J.; Kaplanidou, K.; Kang, S.J. Small-scale event sport tourism: A case study in sustainable tourism. *Sport Manag. Rev.* **2012**, *15*, 160–170. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
3. Higham, J.; Hinch, T. Tourism, sport and seasons: The challenges and potential of overcoming seasonality in the sport and tourism sectors. *Tour. Manag.* **2002**, *23*, 175–185. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
4. Maditinos, Z.; Vassiliadis, C.; Tzavlopoulos, Y.; Vassiliadis, S.A. Sports events and the COVID-19 pandemic: Assessing runners' intentions for future participation in running events—evidence from Greece. *Tour. Recreat. Res.* **2021**, *46*, 276–287. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
5. World Tourism Organization. *International Tourism Highlights, 2023 Edition—The Impact of COVID-19 on Tourism (2020–2022)*, October 2023; UNWTO: Madrid, Spain, 2023. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
6. World Tourism Organization. *Tourism and Rural Development: Understanding Challenges on the Ground—Lessons Learned from the Best Tourism Villages by UNWTO Initiative*; UNWTO: Madrid, Spain, 2023. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
7. Manning, T.; Fayossolà, E.; Weiss, B.; del Río, I.M. *Indicators of Sustainable Development for Tourism Destinations; A Guidebook*; World Tourism Organization: Madrid, Spain, 2004.
8. Sáez-Fernández, F.J.; Jiménez-Hernández, I.; Ostos-Rey, M.D.S. Seasonality and efficiency of the hotel industry in the balearic Islands: Implications for Economic and Environmental Sustainability. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 3506. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
9. Su, Z.; Wen, R.; Zeng, Y.; Ye, K.; Khotphat, T. The influence of seasonality on the sustainability of livelihoods of households in rural tourism destinations. *Sustainability* **2022**, *14*, 10572. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
10. Xie, J. The economic determinants of tourism seasonality: A case study of the Norwegian tourism industry. *Cogent Bus. Manag.* **2020**, *7*, 1732111. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
11. Malchrowicz-Moško, E.; Poczta, J. A small-scale event and a big impact—Is this relationship possible in the world of sport? The meaning of heritage sporting events for sustainable development of tourism—Experiences from Poland. *Sustainability* **2018**, *10*, 4289. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
12. Melo, R.; Andrade, C.S.; Van Rheenen, D.; Sobry, C. Portugal: Small scale sport tourism events and local sustainable development. The case of the III Running Wonders Coimbra. In *Small Scale Sport Tourism Events and Local Sustainable Development: A Cross-National Comparative Perspective*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2021; pp. 173–190.

13. Poczta, J.; Malchrowicz-Moško, E. Modern running events in sustainable development—More than Just taking care of health and physical condition (Poznan Half Marathon Case Study). *Sustainability* **2018**, *10*, 2145. [CrossRef]
14. Reier Forraddellas, R.; Nández Alonso, S.L.; Jorge-Vázquez, J.; Echarte Fernández, M.Á.; Vidal, M.N. Entrepreneurship, sport, sustainability and integration: A business model in the low-season tourism sector. *Soc. Sci.* **2021**, *10*, 117. [CrossRef]
15. Tomino, A.C.; Perić, M.; Wise, N. Assessing and considering the wider impacts of sport-tourism events: A research agenda review of sustainability and strategic planning elements. *Sustainability* **2020**, *12*, 4473. [CrossRef]
16. Heebkhokung, K.; Rattanawong, W.; Vongmanee, V. A New Paradigm of a Sustainability-Balanced Scorecard Model for Sport Tourism. *Sustainability* **2023**, *15*, 10586. [CrossRef]
17. Martins, R.; Pereira, E.; Rosado, A.; Maroco, J.; McCullough, B.; Mascarenhas, M. Understanding spectator sustainable transportation intentions in international sport tourism events. *J. Sustain. Tour.* **2022**, *30*, 1972–1991. [CrossRef]
18. Mazza, B. A Theoretical Model of Strategic Communication for the Sustainable Development of Sport Tourism. *Sustainability* **2023**, *15*, 7039. [CrossRef]
19. Gursoy, D.; Kim, K.; Uysal, M. Perceived impacts of festivals and special events by organizers: An extension and validation. *Tour. Manag.* **2004**, *25*, 171–181. [CrossRef]
20. Kim, K.; Uysal, M.; Chen, J. Festival visitor motivation from the organizers' points of view. *Event Management. Event Manag.* **2001**, *7*, 127–134. [CrossRef]
21. McKelvey, S.; Grady, J. Sponsorship program protection strategies for special sport events: Are event organizers outmaneuvering ambush marketers? *J. Sport Manag.* **2008**, *22*, 550–586. [CrossRef]
22. Chevront, S.N.; Sollanek, K.J.; Fattman, K.; Troyanos, C. Validation of a Mobile Application Water Planning Tool for Road Race Event Organizers. *Med. Sci. Sports Exerc.* **2019**, *51*, 1040–1046. [CrossRef]
23. Gkarane, S.; Vassiliadis, C.A.; Gianni, M. Exploring professionals' perceptions of tourism seasonality and sports events: A qualitative study of Kissavos marathon race. *Enlightening Tourism. A Pathmaking J.* **2022**, *12*, 24–51.
24. Ruhanen, L. Stakeholder participation in tourism destination planning another case of missing the point? *Tour. Recreat. Res.* **2009**, *34*, 283–294. [CrossRef]
25. Parent, M.M.; Eskerud, L.; Hanstad, D.V. Brand creation in international recurring sports events. *Sport Manag. Rev.* **2012**, *15*, 145–159. [CrossRef]
26. Kruger, M.; Saayman, M. Creating a memorable spectator experience at the Two Oceans Marathon. *J. Sport Tour.* **2012**, *17*, 63–77. [CrossRef]
27. Yoopetch, C.; Kongarchapatara, B.; Nimsai, S. Tourism Forecasting Using the Delphi Method and Implications for Sustainable Tourism Development. *Sustainability* **2022**, *15*, 126. [CrossRef]
28. Walo, M.; Bull, A.; Breen, H. Achieving economic benefits at local events: A case study of a local sports event. *Festiv. Manag. Event Tour.* **1996**, *4*, 95–106. [CrossRef]
29. Hair, J., Jr.; Hult, G.T.M.; Ringle, C.M.; Sarstedt, M.; Danks, N.P.; Ray, S. *Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Using R: A Workbook*; Springer Nature: New York, NY, USA, 2021; ISBN 978-3-030-80519-7.
30. Leguina, A. A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). *Int. J. Res. Method Educ.* **2015**, *38*, 220–221. [CrossRef]
31. Hair, J.F.; Black, W.C.; Babin, B.J.; Anderson, R.E. *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 7th ed.; Prentice-Hall: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 2009.
32. Chin, W.W. The Partial Least Squares Approach for Structural Equation Modeling. *Mod. Methods Bus. Res.* **1998**, *295*, 295–336.
33. Henseler, J.; Ringle, C.M.; Sinkovics, R.R. The Use of Partial Least Squares Path Modeling in International Marketing. In *Advances in International Marketing*; Sinkovics, R.R., Ghauri, P.N., Eds.; Emerald Group Publishing Limited: Bingley, UK, 2009; Volume 20, pp. 277–319.
34. Rasoolimanesh, S.M.; Ramakrishna, S.; Hall, C.M.; Esfandiari, K.; Seyfi, S. A systematic scoping review of sustainable tourism indicators in relation to the sustainable development goals. *J. Sustain. Tour.* **2023**, *31*, 1497–1517. [CrossRef]
35. Sharpley, R. Tourism, sustainable development and the theoretical divide: 20 years on. *J. Sustain. Tour.* **2020**, *28*, 1932–1946. [CrossRef]
36. UN. The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2022. 2022. Available online: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2022/> (accessed on 7 December 2023).
37. Pradhan, P. A threefold approach to rescue the 2030 Agenda from failing. *Natl. Sci. Rev.* **2023**, *10*, nwad015. [CrossRef]

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